

Under normal operating condition, the self-excitation, $E_1 \neq 0$ [10], thus

$$Y_1 + Y_M + Y_R = 0 \quad (2)$$

For given value of shaft speed, generator parameters, excitation capacitance and load impedance, we can determine the value of the p.u. output frequency F and The corresponding value of magnetizing reactance X_M .

R_S, R_R, R_L are the per unit (P.U) stator, rotor and load resistances respectively. X_S, X_R, X_M, X_C is the P.U stator, rotor magnetizing and excitation reactance respectively. Y_S, Y_R, Y_M, Y_L, Y_C are the P.U stator, rotor, magnetizing, load and excitation admittances respectively. F , is the P.U frequency. v , is the P.U speed which is the ratio between rotor speed and synchronous speed. I_S, I_R, I_L , are the P.U stator, rotor and load currents respectively. E_g, V_t , are the P.U air gap and terminal voltage respectively.

III. PSO BASED ON SEIG

To ensure the phenomena of self-excitation, (2) must be satisfied. Equation (2) is solved using PSO method to find the values of unknown F and X_M and then determine the value of the terminal voltage. The objective function of the system to be optimized based on the model of Fig.1 is as follows:

$$\text{Let } Y_1 (Y_1, Y_M, Y_R) = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \text{Subject to } 0.9 < F < 0.99 \\ 100 < X_M < 200 \end{array} \right\} \quad (4)$$

Where

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} Y_1 = \frac{(Y_C + Y_L) Y_S}{Y_C + Y_L + Y_S} \quad Y_L = \frac{1}{(R_L / F)} \\ Y_M = \frac{1}{jX_M} \quad Y_C = \frac{1}{(-jX_C / F^2)} \\ Y_S = \frac{1}{(R_S / F) + jX_S} \quad Y_R = \frac{1}{\frac{R_R}{F - v} + jX_R} \end{array} \right\} \quad (5)$$

In this system (2-5), the value of the total admittance is considered as fitness function and the problem space is two dimensions F and X_M . Population size is chosen to be 160, the search will be terminated if the number of iterations reaches 200, or if the number of iterations since the last change of the best solution is greater than 51.

The essential steps of the particle swarm optimization can be summarized as shown in the following flowchart Fig. 2,

Fig. 2 Flowchart for implementation of PSO

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Intensive simulation has been done using MATLAB, for PSO algorithm to find the F and X_M , then used to find the terminal voltage (V_t) of the SEIG and other parameter.

The simulation has been run for different capacitance (C), speed (N) and resistive load (R), Table I gives the details of the different values of C, R and N which presented in [10].

TABLE I
 THE INPUT DATA (N, C, AND R)

Set No.	Speed RPM		C(μ F)	R(Ω)	No. of Samples
	From	To			
1	1435	1570	36	160	6
2	1275	1435	51	160	6
3	1410	1565	36	220	6
4	1290	1425	51	220	6

We choose the range of speed and the value of terminal capacitance to enable the machine to supply power to the connected load at rated voltage. The resistive load is not sensitive to change in frequency. Therefore, the values of load resistance can be chosen arbitrarily.

Fig. 3 Voltage and frequency versus Speed at C=36 μ F and R=160 Ω

Fig. 4 Voltage and Frequency versus Speed at C=36 μ F and R=220 Ω

Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 shows V_t versus N at C=36 μ F and R=160 Ω and 220 Ω respectively, we used the same input data in [9] to compare our result with them. We get this result after the average cumulative change in value of the fitness function over 50 generations, less than $1e-006$ and constraint violation less than $1e-006$, after 102 generations.

Fig. 5 Best fitness function value versus generation

Fig. 6 Initial and current position of the particle swarm

Fig. 7 Number of individuals in each generation

Fig. 5 shows the final best point of the F and X_M which are (1.0333 85.3830) versus the number of the generation stopped at (102 generations).

Fig. 6 shows the initial and final position of the particle swarm position, from the figure the initial position of the particle swarm spread all over the graph but after many iteration the particle swarm settled and cumulative in definite position between 0.94 and 0.95 of the number of initial population range.

Fig. 7 shows a histogram of the scores at each generation. The individual is any point to which one can apply the fitness function.

From the result we found it so close to the result in [9]. Moreover, the PSO method is fast, easy and more accurate than the method in [9].

The various characteristics of the generator can be obtained from its equivalent circuit but that requires running PSO for different possible values of a particular parameter.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, novel method (PSO) is proposed to evaluate the performance characteristics of a SEIG as optimization problem. The PSO simulation results are compared with the previous methods results, it is found reliable, more accurate and the closeness between the results prove the validity of PSO technique as a new algorithm to solve the SEIG characteristics.

APPENDIX [10]

Machine Specifications:

3-Phase, 50 Hz, 2.2 kW/3.0 HP, 4-pole, 230 Volts, 8.6 Amp. Delta connected squirrel cage induction machine.

Machine Parameters:

$R_S = 3.35 \Omega$ $R_R = 1.76 \Omega$ $X_S = 4.85 \Omega$
 $X_R = 4.85 \Omega$

Magnetization characteristics of machine for determination of air gap voltage:

$$E_1 = 344.411 - 1.610 X_M \quad X_M < 82.292$$

$$E_1 = 465.120 - 3.077 X_M \quad 95.569 > X_M \geq 82.292$$

$$E_1 = 579.897 - 4.278 X_M \quad 108.00 > X_M \geq 95.569$$

$$E_1 = 0 \quad X_M > 108.00$$

REFERENCES

- [1] M. H. Haque, "A Novel Method of Evaluating Performance Characteristics of a Self-Excited Induction Generator", IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion, Vol. 24, No. 2, pp.358-365, June 2009.
- [2] Gurgun K., Freere P., "MATLAB symbolic computation for the steady state modeling of symmetrically loaded self excited induction generator", Kathmandu university journal of science, engineering and technology, Vol. I, No. III, pp.1-7, January 2007.
- [3] M. H. Haque, "Analysis of a Self-Excited Induction Generator with P-Q Load Model", IEEE Transaction on Energy Conversion, Vol. 25, No. 1, pp.265-267, March 2010.
- [4] D. Joshi, K. S. Sandhu, and M. K. Soni, "Performance Analysis of Self-Excited Induction Generator Using Artificial Neural Network", Iranian Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Vol. 5, No. 1, pp.57-62 Winter-Spring 2006.
- [5] Raja Singh Khela, R. K. Bansal, K. S. Sandhu, and A. K. Goel, "Cascaded ANN for Evaluation of Frequency and Air-gap Voltage of Self-Excited Induction Generator", World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology 27, pp.301-307, 2007.
- [6] A.A.Arkadan, Y.Abou-Samra, Z.H.Ramadan, "Radial Basis Networks for the Simulation of Stand Alone AC Generators during No-Break Power Transfer", Marquette University, Milwaukee, WI, pp.237-243, 2007.
- [7] S.Mahley, "Steady State Analysis of three phase Self-Excited Induction Generator, Master Thesis, Department of Power Systems and Electric Drives, Thapar University, Patiala, 2008.

- [8] S Singaravelu Dr. S Velusami, "Generalized Steady State Modeling and Analysis of Three Phase Self Excited Induction Generators", International Journal of Emerging Electric Power Systems, Vol. 3, Issue 2, Article 1080, 2005.
- [9] H.E.A.Ibrahim, M.M.Metwaly and M.F.Serag, "Analysis of self excited induction generator (SEIG) using symbolic toolbox and artificial neural network (ANN)", Ain shams journal of electrical engineering (ASJEE), Vol.2, pp.17-28, Dec.2010.
- [10] Raja Singh Khela , Raj Kumar Bansal , K. S. Sandhu and Ashok Kumar Goel, "Application of Artificial Neural Network for Analysis of Self-Excited Induction Generator", JCS and T, Vol. 6, No. 2, pp.73-79, October 2006.
- [11] R.C.Bansal,"Three-Phase Self-Excited Induction Generators:An Overview", IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion, Vol. 20, No. 2, pp.292-299, June 2005.